

University of Nebraska - Lincoln

DigitalCommons@University of Nebraska - Lincoln

Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)

Libraries at University of Nebraska-Lincoln

2019

Use of E-Journals by Library and Information Science Researchers of India: An Empirical Analysis

Khushpreet Singh Brar

Panjab Unicersity, Chandigarh, khushpreet.singh@gmail.com

Bhupinder Singh

Central University of Punjab, Bathinda, brar.cup@gmail.com

Amandeep Kaur

Punjabi University, Patiala, amandeep.kaur.bagri@gmail.com

Follow this and additional works at: <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac>

Part of the [Library and Information Science Commons](#)

Brar, Khushpreet Singh; Singh, Bhupinder; and Kaur, Amandeep, "Use of E-Journals by Library and Information Science Researchers of India: An Empirical Analysis" (2019). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 2431.

<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/2431>

Use of E-Journals by Library and Information Science Researchers of India: An Empirical Analysis

Dr. Khushpreet Singh Brar

Assistant Professor, Department of Library and Information Science
Panjab University, Chandigarh
Email: ksbrar@pu.ac.in

Dr. Bhupinder Singh

Assistant Librarian, Central Library
Central University of Punjab, Bathinda
Email: bhupinder82@gmail.com

Amandeep Kaur

UGC-JRF, Department of Library and Information Science
Punjabi University, Patiala
Email: amandeep.kaur.bagri@gmail.com

Abstract

Purpose- The purpose of the paper is to find out the level of awareness and use of e-journal by the researchers pursuing Ph.D in library and information science.

Design/Methodology/Approach – The data is collected through a well-structured questionnaire from the research scholars of library and information science.

Findings- the study reveals that all the researchers of library and information science are aware about the availability of e-journals. The on screen reading is preferred by majority of researchers and the HTML is the preferred format. But the less number of researchers prefer or published their research paper in e-journals.

Research limitation/implications – the present paper consists only of e-journals users of library and information science subject and scope is restricted to research scholars only. The scope of the study can be

extended to other subjects and undergraduate, post graduate students and faculty of the universities.

Originality/Value – there are many studies on the use of e-journals, but this is the first of its kind based on the library and information science researchers.

Keywords – electronic journals, user studies, research, universities, India

Paper type – Research Paper

Introduction

The desire of man for preserving and disseminating his thoughts and ideas is perceptibly inherent in his nature. Reasonably, he has been exercising various means, modes and methods to fulfill the same desire since the time immemorial. The means and methods used by man to preserve his ideas were accordingly and complementary to the age and society in which he existed. Hence these means and methods varied due the variations of time and diversities of societies. Earlier, the stone, clay tablet and papyrus were used for the purpose. The invention of paper (in 105 A.D. by Tsai Lun) and then the printing press (in 1440 A.D. by Gutenberg) were the revolutionary changes in the field. These two inventions totally transformed, advanced and modernized the function of dissemination and preservation of thoughts and ideas. Since then, the books, periodicals and journals have been consistently published for the circulation, preservation and maintenance of thoughts and ideas. Till the later decades of seventeenth century, the dissemination and communication of ideas among scholars were predominantly depended on the personal contacts of the scholars to each other and arrangement of formal meetings by the learned societies. Reasonably, with the passage of time, the membership of these scholarly societies increased that made it unfeasible for all aspirants of knowledge to formally attend these meetings. To make the knowledge reach to possibly maximum of its aspirants, the proceedings of the formal scholarly meetings were generally circulated. These proceedings were initially the means for the scholars to publish their thoughts in the form of

papers and articles. The trend, certainly getting more systematic and technical with the passage of time has moved towards the established source of scholarly knowledge that we now recognize as scholarly journals. The development and advancement in information communication technologies prove another benchmark in it. The printed documents, books, journals are shifted to electronic format to save the time, cost, efforts, environment, etc.

Objectives of the Study

The study an attempt to fulfill following objectives:

1. To explore the use of electronic journals by researchers of Library and Information Science (LIS).
2. To identify the users' (researcher) preference for format of e-journals.
3. To check the relevance and usefulness of electronic journals.
4. To explore the publication of researchers in e-journals.
5. To ascertain the effect of e-journals.

Review of Literature

Singh (2009) has discussed the print and e-journals in detail. The author stated the definitions, differences, merits and demerits of the print as well as the e-journals. The author also justified the transaction of print to electronic media by discussing the advanced features of it.

Brar (2012) conducted a survey of library users of Punjabi university Patiala to examine the awareness and use of e-journals. The author collected the data with the help of questionnaire and presented graphically using the percentage. The study disclosed the purpose of using e-journals, location of accessing e-journals, frequency of use, and level of satisfaction of the library users.

Amandeep and others (2017) studied the use of the Internet for reading. The study is based on primary data collected from postgraduate students and Ph.D. researchers of Punjabi university, Patiala. The paper presents the results of 80 students and researchers on the various parameters. The study reveals that the students and researchers were more dependable on the Internet and e-resources than printed publications.

Bhupinder and others (2017) conducted a survey of 500 students from different universities of north India for examine the utilization of Internet based resources. A structured questionnaire was used for collection of data. The study discovered that all the students were using the internet and internet based sources and services. To get required information, search engines, websites, e-resources, subject gateways, portals, blogs, and Wikipedia were used in order of preference. Majority of the students had knowledge and awareness about social networking sites.

Bajpai and other (2017) checked the awareness and use of electronic resources. The study was conducted on selected special libraries of Delhi. The author discovered the purpose and difficulties in using e-resources and satisfaction level of the users with the available electronic resources. The study disclosed that 58.5% library reader visit library daily. 87.1% users are aware about different search engines, 84.2% aware about e-journals and e-books. Majority of the users (61%) use e-resources for their course work/ study material followed by research work (57.7%) and to get current information (55.9%). The study also explored that the users are facing many technical problems while accessing the e-journals and e-resources.

In another paper Brar, Kaur and Kaur (2018) studied the awareness and acceptance of e-journals among the researchers of library and information science. The study reveals that the all the researchers of library and information science subject are aware about the e-journals of the field. They also studied the preferred format, purpose, frequency of use of e-

journals. Searching patron and number wise monthly usage of e-journals are also revealed in this paper.

Research Methodology

In the present study, the Ph.D. researchers of the subject of library and information science from various universities of India were selected randomly. A structured questionnaire was prepared for collection of data. The data was collected personally and through email. The Complete and valid questionnaires of 120 Ph.D. Researches were selected, thoroughly analysed, tabulated and graphically represented in this study

Limitation of the Study

The study consists only of e-journals users of library and information science subject and scope is restricted to research scholars only. The study does not include the other subjects except library and information science. It also does not cover the undergraduate, post graduate students and faculty of the universities.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Methods of reading the e-journals

In general, there are two methods of reading the e-journals, i.e. on screen and print on paper. While realising it relevant to know the method adopted by the researchers to read the full text, the relevant query was asked from the respondents. In response 37.50 per cent respondents asserted that they got a print on paper to read out a full article from e-journals, while the remaining 62.50 revealed that they read the full text on screen.

Fig. 1: Methods of reading the e-journals

The data corroborates that there are minority of researchers who get a print on paper to read out full text e-journals and the noticeable majority of researchers prefer to read out e-journals on screen. There are number of reasons for the prevalence of that trend among researchers. Firstly, there is dearth of printers and papers among researchers to print out every article to read. Secondly, the printing facilities available around, are costly for them to afford frequently. Thirdly, in today's age of technology, most of the researchers have their personal laptops or desktops to access, download and save the e-journals' articles to read any time on screen.

Preference to particular format of information display

Further, it was asked from the researchers to ascertain that what format of information display they prefer in e-journals. In response, 59.17 per cent of the respondents confirmed that they preferred HTML format, while the PDF format had been confirmed as preferred by 40 per cent of respondents. In addition, only 0.83 per cent respondents gave their preference to the DOC format.

Fig. 2: Preference to particular format of information display

The data confirms that most of the researchers prefer HTML format as it is a dynamic in style, displaying quality graphics, multimedia and hyperlink features. The PDF format occupies second preference due to its print-friendly features. The DOC format is given the least priority as it can be easily edited and hence altered by anyone. Due to these drawbacks, the DOC format is least used format in e-journals.

Relevance, Usefulness and Value of e-journals

While examining the use of e-journals, it is relevant to study the relevance, usefulness and value of e-journals for the information seekers. Considering this, four types of variables of the usefulness of the e-journals were given to respondents and they were asked to notify their preferences. While responding, 47.50 per cent of the respondents confirmed the e-journals as Most Helpful. Other 50 per cent respondents noticed an Average usefulness of e-journals, while 2.50 per cent of the respondents considered the e-journals as Little Helpful in their research. Noticeably, none of the respondents had considered the fourth variable, i.e. Not Helpful.

Fig.: 3: Relevance, Usefulness and Value of e-journals

The data verifies that e-journals are invariably considered as most helpful for the approximate half of the researchers. For other half of the researchers, the e-journals occupy an average usefulness. Only a negligible number of researchers (2.5 per cent) consider the e-journal as little helpful and not even single respondent considers the e-journals as not being useful.

Subscription of the ToC of the relevant e-journals

For the regular and frequent reader of e-journals, it is helpful to subscribe via e-mail, the Table of Contents (ToC) of the e-journals. Therefore, it was asked from the researchers that whether they have subscribed via e-mail, the subscription of the ToC of the relevant e-journals. The responses of the respondents revealed that 59.17 per cent researchers had subscribed the ToC of the e-journals while the other 40.83 had not subscribed the same.

Fig. 4: Subscription of the ToC of the relevant e-journals

The general depiction of the data is that though immense majority of the researchers have subscribed the ToC on their e-mails, still noticeable number of researchers have not subscribed it. A thorough analysis of the concern exposes reasonable causes for the same. The researchers who probably find any journal/s relevant to their research area usually subscribe the ToC of the particular journal/s. considerably there is dearth of variety of journals to deal with every research area of the subject. Hence, the researchers, who do not find the e-journal relevant to their research area, do not usually subscribe the ToC of e-journals and prefer to find out the e-journals with help of the search engines and other sources.

Usefulness of subscription of ToC service

All the 59.17 per researchers, when asked to reveal the usefulness of the subscription of the ToC, had considered the subscription of e-journals as useful. It verifies the fact the subscription of ToC of the e-journals is significant for the researchers to supplement their research.

Fig. 5: Usefulness of subscription of ToC service

Recommendation of e-journals to other information seekers

Further, it was enquired from the respondents that whether they recommended the e-journals to other students. Positively, 100 per cent of the respondents admitted they had recommended the e-journals to the others also.

Fig. 6: Recommendation of e-journals to other information seekers

The data asserts that all the researchers recommend the e-journals to the students and other information seekers. It further confirms the significance and reliability of e-journals among the researchers.

Publication or submission of articles in e-journals

It was realised from a comprehensive research's viewpoint to ask the respondents that whether they had submitted or published any of their articles to the open access e-journals. Interestingly, as many as 47.50 per cent respondents have confirmed that they submitted or got published their article/s in the open access e-journals. However, 52.50 per cent of the respondents had not done the same so far.

Fig. 7: Publication or submission of articles in e-journals

The notion that majority of the researchers have not published or submitted their articles in the open access e-journals should not be considered as an unenthusiastic trend of researchers towards the e-journals. Reasonably, A noticeable number of the researchers are at the initial stage of their research work and have not yet developed their article-writing skills and aptitude manifestly. Moreover, the preference given by 47.50 per cent researchers to the e-journals to get their articles published in them, expresses the acceptance and authenticity of the e-journals.

Recommending and supporting others for publication

After examining the interest of the researchers in getting their articles published in the e-journals, other related query was to know whether the researchers recommended and supported others to get their articles

published in the e-journals. Positively, 100 per cent of the respondents responded that they recommended and supported others for the same.

Fig. 8: Recommending and supporting others for publication

The encouragement and support by all the researchers to other associates (scholars, colleagues) to publish papers in the e-journals again strongly verifies the acknowledgement and acceptance of e-journals among the researchers. The e-journals are not only preferred by the researchers themselves to publish their papers but other seekers are also encouraged and even supported by them for the same.

Extent of effect of the use of e-journals

It is significant to examine from those who use frequently the e-journals, the extent of effect of the use of e-journals. To verify the same, it was asked from the respondents that whether the access to e-journals had increased their ability of research and teaching. As many as 85 per cent of the respondents admitted that the access to e-journals had enhanced their research and teaching abilities; however remaining 15 per cent had totally or partially denied that.

Fig. 9: Extent of effect of the use of e-journals

The data corroborates that regular access to the e-journals has actually holistically enhanced the research and teaching abilities of the enormous majority of researchers. The negligible number of researchers who could not recognise the relevance of the access of e-journals to increase their research and teaching abilities are probably those who access the e-journals less frequently.

Conclusion

E-journals are the technological addition to the category of journals. Undoubtedly, awareness of e-journals among the students, researchers and the academicians has been constantly and rapidly increasing. Obviously, the increasing awareness has accelerated the access and use of e-journals among the information seekers. The relevance of the awareness and use of e-journals in the subject of LIS acquires more prerequisite significance. While examining empirically and observing analytically the scale and scope of awareness, access and use of e-journals among researchers, it establishes as an obvious fact that the researchers are keen interested in reading the papers on screen of their electronic gadgets and the HTML format is more preferable. The researchers feels the e-journals are helpful and majority of them are subscribing the table of content

service on their email. E-journals are becoming the popular medium of publication among the researchers.

References

- Amandeep Kaur, B. Singh and K. S. Brar (2017) Use of the Internet for Reading: A Case Study of Punjabi University, Patiala. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*. 6 (5): 01-09.
- Bajpai, P. N. and Sharma, S. (2017). Awareness and use of electronic resources in special libraries of Delhi NCR. *International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology*, 7(4): 272-275.
- Bhupinder Singh, Amandeep Kaur and K. S. Brar (2017) Awareness and Use of Internet based Sources: A Case study of North India. *Innovation the Research Concept*. 2 (7): 67-71
- Brar, K S (2012) User awareness and use of electronic journals at the Punjabi university, Patiala: a study. *International journal of library and information studies*, 2(1): 48-55.
- Brar, Khushpreet Singh; Navkiran Kaur and Amandeep Kaur (2018). Awareness and acceptance of e-journals among Researchers of LIS: An empirical analysis. *International journal of information studies & Libraries*, 3(1): 13-17